

Metal Assisted Chemical Etching of porous silicon for Photo Voltaic Application

Ragavendran Venkatesan¹, Muthu Kumar Arivalagan¹, Vishnukanthan Venkatachalapathy²,
JeyanthinathMayandi^{1,*}

^{1,*}Department of Materials Science, School of Chemistry, Madurai Kamaraj University, Madurai-
625 021, India.

²Centre for Materials Science and Nanotechnology, University of Oslo, PO Box 1032, Blindern, N-
0315 Oslo,
Norway

Email id: jeyanthinath@yahoo.co.in

Recently, metal-assisted chemical etching (MACE) has been proposed as a promising method for the fabrication of porous silicon. Here we report on MACE of Cz-Silicon by varying the etching time for a constant silver nanoparticles (~80 nm) as the catalyst. Porous silicon (PSI) layer properties such as porosity, thickness and depth of the pores were determined. The surface morphology was examined using scanning electron microscopy, the cross sectional SEM image on PSI reveals the depth of the pore and their characteristic feature. The optical properties of the porous silicon layers were examined by diffused reflectance method. The observed results was discussed with respect to different etching time. The various experimental aspects intervening in manufacture and the characterization of the thin layers of porous silicon for photovoltaic application were studied.

Keywords: MACE, porous silicon, etching time and SEM

